

Thermal studies on light basic Magnesium Carbonate

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THE formation of very light and active magnesium oxide by thermal decomposition of magnesium carbonate has created more interest in thermal studies. Hence, several workers¹⁻¹¹ have studied the decomposition by d.t.a. Only few authors⁸⁻¹¹ have observed a sharp exothermic peak following two main endothermic peaks and different explanations have been put forward for this effect. In view of the above conflicting reports, a systematic investigation on d.t.a. of light basic magnesium carbonate was undertaken and the results are reported in this paper.

Experimental

D.t.a. curves were recorded on a Sargent recorder Model M.R. with Chromel-alumel thermocouples. By recording the differential temperature on a chart, it was possible to observe even small or very rapid changes in the test sample. Sensitivity for ΔT scale was about 0.6°/mm. Stainless steel block with drilled in cups of 8 mm dia and 12 mm depth was used as a sample holder. The rate of heating was kept at 10°/min and the temperatures were recorded from the reference cup containing calcined alumina. The thermocouples were calibrated using standard substances for the accuracy of temperatures. Light basic magnesium carbonates from different sources as well as the one prepared in this laboratory from bittern and soda ash were used in the present studies.

Results and Discussion

Curve nos. 1, 2 and 3 (Fig. 1) are those of (i) Chemical reagent grade (Albright and Wilson Ltd., London), (ii) Translucent grade (Darlington, U.S.A.) and (iii) commercial grade prepared in the laboratory from bittern. In the first two curves, the two endothermic peaks at 315° and 415° are followed by two sharp and distinct exothermic peaks. The two endotherms represent dehydration and decomposition accompanied by loss of water of hydration and hydroxyl water respectively^{2,3}. The sharp exothermic peaks are distinctly observed in the first two samples but are absent in the d.t.a. curve for the magnesium carbonate sample prepared in this laboratory. The magnitudes of the endotherms are also considerably different. Samples (i) and (ii) always show the two exothermic effects though the relative heights of the first to the second exotherms are differ-

ent in both the samples, however, the peak temperatures are the same, i.e., 475° and 485°.

Soleimanov¹⁰ explained the exotherm at 500° as being due to the reaction of evolved carbon dioxide with magnesium hydroxide. No satisfactory explanation was proposed by Webb¹¹ while observing a small exothermic effect to be a characteristic of most magnesite samples he examined by d.t.a. Dell and Weller⁸ attributed this effect to recrystallization of magnesite. While Rao *et al.*⁹ have explained the exotherm to be caused by the removal of internal crystal defects in the metastable oxide lattice.

In the present studies two exotherms are observed of which the second one is observed at 485° and this exotherm is close to that observed by Dell and Weller⁸. The X-ray diffraction patterns of the samples heated to 480° show two faint lines of magnesite alongwith broad lines of magnesia but those heated at 540° show only broad lines of magnesium oxide. This observation clearly indicates that some carbondioxide is lost in the temperature range 480°-540°. However, weight loss studies indicated following reactions to occur:

First stage

Second stage

N.B. The composition of the sample from M/s. Albright and Wilson was reported to be $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 3\text{MgCO}_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

However, weight loss in presence of chloride ions shows complete conversion to magnesium oxide when heated to 540°.

The d.t.a. behaviour of the commercial grade sample is entirely different from those of the imported light basic magnesium carbonates though the endotherms around 315° and 415° are at the same temperature as for the imported samples. However, the course of further reaction is not exemplified either by an endotherm or by an exotherm. Under the conditions of preparation, it could be expected that magnesium chloride may be the chief impurity retained by magnesium carbonate precipitate. The analysis of the samples presented in Table 1 shows the presence of 0.53% chloride as compared to only 0.05% in the imported material. Therefore, the sample was further washed by stirring in warm water (50°) for 15 min. After filtering and drying at 100°, the d.t.a. of this sample was made (Curve 4, Fig. 1). The d.t.a. behaviour of this sample was found to be very similar to that of the imported samples.

It is, therefore, clear that the chloride ion impurity has a marked effect on the d.t.a. characteristics of light basic magnesium carbonate. A systematic study has been made by doping sample No. 1 with 0.2% magnesium chloride, 0.2% sodium chloride and 2% sodium chloride. The d.t.a. of these samples are presented as curve Nos. 5, 6 and 7 (Fig. 1). It can be readily seen that chloride doped samples

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Fig. 1. D.T.A. of Basic Magnesium Carbonates $4\text{MgCO}_3 \cdot \text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

have a very different thermal behaviour as compared to the pure sample (Curve No. 1). Further, it may be noted that 2% NaCl (corresponding to

TABLE I—COMPOSITION OF LIGHT BASIC MAGNESIUM CARBONATE SAMPLES

Content (%)	1	2	3	4*
MgO	42.50	42.31	42.50	42.35
CO ₂	36.75	36.65	37.20	37.30
Cl	0.05	0.03	0.53	0.06

* Washed with warm water.

about 1% chloride ions) produces the same effect as 0.2% MgCl₂ (corresponding to only 0.14% chloride ions). However, the sample containing 0.2% NaCl

shows three distinct endotherms but no exothermic effect.

Berg¹² obtained similar results during his studies on dolomites and found that the decomposition temperatures were considerably lowered in presence of alkali metal salts. In fact addition of sodium chloride actually changed the ratio of the areas in the d.t.a. within wide limits. The appearance of exotherms thereby reflects on the absence of ionic impurities.

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Derivatization of aliphatic amines as benzylthiuronium dithiocarbamates

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THE derivatization of amines as benzylthiuronium dithiocarbamates¹ was reported as a valuable procedure. The procedure requires the preparation of an almost neutral solution of an ammonium dithiocarbamate. The preparation of such a solution is a bit inconvenient because the dithiocarbamic acids tend to decompose if the pH falls below 7 and if the pH is above 7 the derivative is contaminated by the